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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**10. Ukrainian State Border Control: Legislative
Support for the Prevention of Violations. By
YAROSLAV KUSHNIR. P. 201.**

CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH-DENMARK

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(10)

UKRAINIAN STATE BORDER CONTROL: LEGISLATIVE SUPPORT FOR THE PREVENTION OF VIOLATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The prevention of cross-border crime is essential to law enforcement agencies that guard state borders. This function is vested in the State Border Guard Service (SBGS) in Ukraine. Although Ukrainian legislation provides for several legal documents and initiatives regulating border activities, it is important to determine their effectiveness in combating typical cross-border offences, namely smuggling, illegal migration and official misconduct that facilitates crime. Our study aimed to determine the effectiveness of legal documents and initiatives to prevent border crime by analysing the dynamics of court decisions related to the State Border Guard Service. The research used the methods of induction, deduction, analysis, statistical comparison, and trend analysis. The study's results revealed the insufficient effectiveness of preventive measures to prevent smuggling and illegal migration and the low level of prevention of violations of job descriptions related to the actions or inaction of SBGS employees. The increase in the level of violations of job descriptions in recent years may be due to new requirements for STS employees during the martial law period or the low effectiveness of anti-corruption measures.

Keywords: *regulatory and legal regulation, prevention, prevention of offences, State Border Guard Service of Ukraine, smuggling, court decisions, job descriptions, corruption, illegal migration.*

1- INTRODUCTION

The State Border Guard Service of Ukraine ensures the inviolability of the state border. It controls the state's sovereign rights observance at the border and in maritime zones. The functions of the Border Guard Service include preventive measures that prevent illegal migration, illegal movement of goods and cargo across the border, and violation of the demarcation line¹. Prevention of offences plays an important role in the activities of border guards at various levels, as crime prevention ensures national security and the population's well-being. Despite the development of regulatory initiatives to prevent offences at the state border, assessing their effectiveness in court decisions related to the SBGS and major cross-border crimes is important.

The study aims to determine the effectiveness of legal documents and initiatives to regulate the prevention of offences at the state border by analysing the dynamics of court decisions related to the State Border Guard Service, including smuggling, illegal migration, and border guards' violations of job descriptions.

Literature review

Prevention of border crime is of great importance in the law enforcement system of different countries, as cross-border crime poses a threat of illegal migration, smuggling, terrorism and other risks². EU countries have developed an integrated model for controlling and regulating the cross-border movement of people, goods and cargo, which includes cooperation at the interagency, intra-agency and international levels³. Intra-agency cooperation ensures compliance with the country's legislation on access to persons, goods, and services under the conditions determined by the state's jurisdiction⁴. Interagency cooperation helps to counteract situational crime that accompanies cross-border crime, namely organised crime related to international smuggling, trafficking in

¹ Law of Ukraine "On the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine" No. 661-IV of 2003. *Verhovna Rada of Ukraine*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/661-15#Text>

² García Pinzón, V., & Mantilla, J. (2021). Contested borders: organised crime, governance, and bordering practices in the Colombia-Venezuela borderlands. *Trends in Organised Crime*, 24(2), 265-281. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12117-020-09399-3>

³ Wagner, J. (2021). The European Union's model of Integrated Border Management: preventing transnational threats, cross-border crime and irregular migration in the context of the EU's security policies and strategies. *Commonwealth & Comparative Politics*, 59(4), 424-448. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14662043.2021.1999650>

⁴ Upreti, Y. (2022). APF Command and Staff College A Study of Inter-Agency Cooperation in Border Governance of Nepal. *Journal of APF Command and Staff College*, 5(1), 109-130. https://scholar.googleusercontent.com/scholar?q=cache:LQy0oNAnh50J:scholar.google.com/+interdepartmental+interaction+border+services+&hl=uk&as_sdt=0.5&as_ylo=2021

illegal drugs, illegal migration and money laundering⁵. Moreover, approaches to controlling illegal activities at the borders differ depending on the offences involved. For example, the southern borders of the EU are guarded by armed military or gendarmes, as there is a risk of terrorism and the transit of radicals and foreign fighters. At the same time, the eastern borders are often guarded by demilitarised police units, as these borders are more prone to smuggling, corruption and money laundering⁶. The United States also uses paramilitary police units to protect the state border from drug traffickers and illegal migrants. In some areas, the military, together with the police, provide security. In contrast, in others, military equipment, aerial reconnaissance capabilities, military transport, technical support for equipment, and military participation in the construction of the border zone are used⁷.

On the one hand, preventive measures at the border protect the country from the risks associated with smuggling, illegal migration and terrorism. However, on the other hand, the policy of externalising migration control violates migrants' rights⁸. Namely, third-country nationals are denied access to EU countries or expelled without a prior examination of their case. Even though such a policy contradicts the fair access to the right to asylum by migrants and the prohibition of collective expulsions, the European Court of Human Rights increasingly does not see violations of the Human Rights Convention in externalisation policies⁹.

The policy of expulsion and deportation is also widespread in the United States, and according to Martínez¹⁰, it is increasingly racialised, which causes the separation of families of Latin American origin, as deportations appear to be massive against the backdrop of the systematic criminalisation of undocumented immigrants. Baylis¹¹ expresses a rather radical position and believes that even though the United States stands for democracy and human rights, the country's immigration policy is harsh and

⁵ Brandariz, J. A. (2022). Criminalisation or instrumentalism? New trends in the field of border criminology. *Theoretical Criminology*, 26(2), 285-303 <https://doi.org/10.1177/13624806211009158>

⁶ Russo, A., & Stambøl, E. M. (2022). The external dimension of the EU's fight against transnational crime: Transferring political rationalities of crime control. *Review of International Studies*, 48(2), 326-345. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210521000358>

⁷ Dunn, T. J. (2021). The militarisation of the US-Mexico border in the twenty-first century and implications for human rights. In *Handbook on human security, borders and migration* (pp. 35-53). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781839108907.00007>

⁸ Robinson, C. (2023). Offshoring and Outsourcing Anti-Smuggling Policy: Capacity Building and the Geopolitics of Migrant Smuggling. *Geopolitics*, 29(1), 13-38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14650045.2022.2159385>

⁹ Mitsilegas, V. (2022). The EU external border as a site of preventive (in) justice. *European Law Journal*, 28(4-6), 263-280. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eulj.12444>

¹⁰ Martínez, D. E. (2022). The racialised dimensions of contemporary immigration and border enforcement policies and practices. *Public Administration Review*, 82(3), 598-603. <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.13496>

¹¹ Baylis, E. (2022). White Supremacy, Police Brutality, and Family Separation: Preventing Crimes Against Humanity Within the United States. *University of Illinois Law Review*, 1475. <http://ssrn.com/abstract=3848729>.

sometimes borders on crimes against humanity. Although forced deportation is aimed at reducing the level of organised crime in the country, it can have the opposite effect. For example, when Mexicans are deported from the United States, especially those with criminal records, they are sent to the Tamaulipas region, which is known for its violence and drug trafficking organisations, which is unlikely to reduce drug trafficking at the US border¹².

Illegal migration is a threat that is also associated with human trafficking, so preventing illegal border crossings is a preventive measure of this crime. In order to control the illegal movement of people across the border, statistical information is collected to identify trends and patterns that help counteract illegal transit of people¹³. Trafficking in human beings is characterised by cruelty and complexity, and even though it is countered at the state level, it is difficult to combat, especially among countries with low economic wealth¹⁴. That is why it is important that economically developed countries contribute to the fight against irregular migration both at their borders and neighbouring countries' borders¹⁵. Strict border crossing rules may provoke migrants to smuggle. This effect causes a blurring of the categories of "migrant" and "smuggler", which is associated with the migrant's prolonged vulnerability and pressure from the host state and its law enforcement agencies¹⁶.

Smuggling is one of the biggest economic dangers that threatens a country's economy that cannot fight it. Administrative fines are an important means of combating smuggling, as they become an obstacle for smugglers¹⁷. Patrols, walls, cameras, and other means of detecting the illegal transport of goods are also effective. On the one hand, border equipment helps to strengthen control over possible offences, but it also pushes illegal migrants to seek dangerous routes that cause deaths while trying to get to

¹² Slack, J., & Martínez, D. E. (2021). Postremoval geographies: Immigration enforcement and organised crime on the US-Mexico border. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 111(4), 1062-1078. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2020.1791039>

¹³ Pryimachenko, D., Ivanskyi, A., Lipynskyi, V., Matvieiev, O., & Povoroznik, A. (2021). Counteracting illegal border crossing and human trafficking: comparative analysis. *Amazonia Investiga*, 10(42), 196-205. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2021.42.06.18>

¹⁴ Chilufya, L. B., Ng'andu, P., & Lusaka, Z. (2023). Human Trafficking: A Case of Trans-Border Organised Crime in Zambia. *International Affairs and Global Strategy*, 99, 30-37. <https://doi.org/10.7176/IAGS/99-04>

¹⁵ Schloenhardt, A. (2021). *Migrant smuggling: Illegal migration and organised crime in Australia and the Asia Pacific region* (Vol. 8). Brill.

¹⁶ Augustova, K., Carrapico, H., & Obradović-Wochnik, J. (2021). Becoming a Smuggler: Migration and Violence at EU External Borders. *Geopolitics*, 28(2), 619-640. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14650045.2021.1961223>

¹⁷ Kulish, A., Yunin, O., Us, O., Shapovalova, I., & Yaromii, I. 2021. Smuggling as a threat to economic security of the state, *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 8(3), 384-399. [https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2021.8.3\(25\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2021.8.3(25))

the United States and Europe^{18, 19}. In 2023, around 8,500 migrants went missing or died at EU borders²⁰. Another aspect is that the technological equipment used by borders is effective only if state border guards are honest. Otherwise, corruption creates smuggling flows in which highly skilled smugglers move illegal goods smoothly and low-skilled smugglers “create statistics” for the fight against smuggling²¹.

Thus, the literature review identified prevention as an important means of protecting borders, national and economic security and human rights. Among the main crimes that require the application of effective preventive measures by border authorities are smuggling and human trafficking. At the same time, it is worth noting that the activities of law enforcement agencies that guard the border play an important role, as their actions can facilitate smuggling and illegal migration through corruption schemes. Therefore, our study aimed to determine the effectiveness of preventive measures taken by the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine in preventing smuggling, illegal migration, and violations of job descriptions while performing their duties to protect the state border.

Materials and methods

To achieve the research objective, we have formulated the following tasks: to identify the main preventive measures aimed at protecting the state border; to analyse court cases with the request “State Border Guard Service” in the dynamics over the past 18 years and in the main areas (combating smuggling, illegal migration and violations of job descriptions by employees of the State Border Guard Service). The study used bibliographic, analytical, induction, deduction, graphical trend comparison, and identification methods. We identified the preventive measures of the State Border Guard Service and the relevant regulations and initiatives that correspond to them, which we structured and presented as a table. Based on the open database of the Unified State Register of Court Decisions²², we analysed court cases for the period from 2006 to 2024 using the search query “State Border Guard Service”, “State Border Guard Service,

¹⁸ Boyce, G. A., & Chambers, S. N. (2021). The corral apparatus: counterinsurgency and the architecture of death and deterrence along the Mexico/United States border. *Geoforum*, 120, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2021.01.007>

¹⁹ Chambers, S. N., Boyce, G. A., Launius, S., & Dinsmore, A. (2019). Mortality, Surveillance and the Tertiary "Funnel Effect" on the U.S.-Mexico Border: A Geospatial Modelling of the Geography of Deterrence. *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 36(3), 443-468. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08865655.2019.1570861>

²⁰ McAuliffe, M., & Oucho, L. A. (2024). Report overview: migration continues to be part of the solution in a rapidly changing world, but key challenges remain. *World Migration Report, 2024(1)*, e00033. https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/pub2023-047-l-world-migration-report-2024_13.pdf

²¹ Kim, D., & Tajima, Y. (2022). Smuggling and border enforcement. *International Organisation*, 76(4), 830-867. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002081832200011X>

²² Unified State Register of Court Decisions. (n. d.). <https://reyestr.court.gov.ua/Page/5>

smuggling”, “State Border Guard Service, migration/illegal migration”, “State Border Guard Service, job descriptions”. We presented the data in graphs, performed a trend analysis in Excel, and identified trends in court decisions based on the above requests.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2-1: NORMATIVE AND LEGAL REGULATION OF THE PREVENTION OF OFFENSES AT THE BORDER OF UKRAINE

The main measures to prevent, deter, and combat border offences are set out in the Laws of Ukraine, “On the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine” and “On Border Control,” government programmes, and internal regulations of the State Border Guard Service Administration. Table 1 presents the list of preventive measures and the relevant legal acts or initiatives. The table indicates the years of adoption of the relevant legal acts for further comparison with trends concerning Border Guard Service court cases.

Table 1. Preventive measures of the State Tax Service

Preventive measures of the State Tax Service	Regulations and initiatives
Protection of the border area, patrolling the border area	Law of Ukraine “On the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine” of 2003
Joint patrols with EU countries and the Republic of Moldova	Protocols and agreements on joint patrolling of the Ukrainian-Polish, Ukrainian-Hungarian, Ukrainian-Slovak, Ukrainian-Romanian, and Ukrainian-Moldovan borders of 2010-2016
Creation of “mobile forces”, which included mobile border outposts of border guard detachments, regional departments, a mobile border guard detachment	Programme for the Development of Mobile Units of the State Tax Service of 2015
Establishment of community groups to be involved in law enforcement in border areas	The Law of Ukraine “On the Participation of Citizens in the Protection of Public Order and the State Border” of 2000
Modern equipment with high-tech means for state border protection	The State Programme “Arrangement and Reconstruction of the State Border” of 2015
Analysing and controlling the risks of offences in the border area	Law of Ukraine. “On Border Control of 2010 Programme for the Development of Risk Analysis in the State Tax Service of 2006, 2016 Instruction and Order of the STS Administration “On the Organisation of Risk Analysis” of 2017
Maritime security	Agreement with the Government of the French

	Republic "On official support for strengthening maritime security and safety of Ukraine" of 2019
Arrangement of a new border with a rocky road and modern surveillance complexes	The programme for the development of the state border with the construction of engineering and fortification structures until 2024-2031
Development of border aviation	The 2015 Aviation Development Programme of the State Tax Service
Prevention of unlawful acts or omissions by STS officials	Instruction on the Procedure for the Actions of Officials of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine of 2016

Source: Created by the author based on State Border Guard Service of Ukraine²³

The primary preventive measure taken by the SBGS is round-the-clock border protection, which includes the duty of border guard detachments and monitoring of the border area with the help of equipped observation points, drones, and surveillance cameras. The procedure for patrolling and monitoring compliance with the border regime is set out in the instructions on the procedure for the actions of SBGS officials. Among the auxiliary preventive measures, the latest technologies play an important role in the construction of a new technological border, which reduces the number of border patrols and increases the possibility of remote surveillance.

2-2: EFFECTIVENESS AND TRENDS IN COMBATING CRIMES AT THE BORDERS

An important step in adequate border protection is identifying potentially dangerous areas based on the analysis of crime statistics and assessing patterns and risks arising in different parts of the state border. Cooperation with international partners, such as joint patrols, providing intelligence on problematic areas of the common border, and reporting on detected offences at the international border, is also important in assessing risks. International cooperation also involves exchanging experience on practical approaches to border protection, training in new technologies, and risk assessment.

In addition to international cooperation, interagency cooperation involves exchanging information between law enforcement agencies and plays an important role. Thus, based on court decisions and at the request of the prosecutor's office, the Security Service of Ukraine, the police and other agencies, the STS provides information on the crossing of the Ukrainian border by persons who are participants or witnesses of offences. On the other hand, law enforcement agencies provide the SBGS with information related to cross-border organised crime, which helps establish patterns of border violations and risk analysis.

²³ State Border Guard Service of Ukraine (n. d.). *Official website*. <https://dpsu.gov.ua/ua/border-surveillance>

To assess the effectiveness of preventive measures to prevent offences at the state border, we analysed court decisions on the requests “State Border Guard Service”, “smuggling”, “illegal migration”, and “job descriptions” in the register of court decisions for the period from 2006 to 2024. The choice of requests was based on the primary border offences identified through literature analysis, namely the movement of prohibited goods across the border, illegal transit of people, and violations of the job descriptions of border guards, including corruption or inaction in their duties. We have identified trends over the past 18 years and compared the results with the chronology of legal documents presented in Table 1. Figures 1a and 1b demonstrate the dynamics of court decisions with the query “State Border Guard Service”.

Figure 1. Dynamics (a) and trend line (b) of court decisions on the request “State Border Guard Service”

Source: Created by the author based on the Unified State Register of Court Decisions²⁴

As can be seen from the graph in Figure 1b, the number of court decisions with the query “State Border Guard Service” is increasing, which is described by a polynomial relationship with a probability of further growth $R^2 = 0.9393$. This trend is explained by increased regulations and initiatives that constantly improve approaches to combating offences. Many court decisions are related to requests for information from other law enforcement agencies regarding persons held administratively or criminally liable. This indicates a positive assessment of interagency cooperation, contributing to the fight against crime. However, despite the many prevention measures based on regulatory documents, the number of court decisions on detected border offences is still growing. This trend indicates inadequate preventive regulation of offences at the state border. In order to determine the peculiarities of offences and the effectiveness of their prevention, we analysed the dynamics of court decisions on the request “State Border Guard Service, smuggling” (Figures 2a, 2b), “State Border Guard Service, illegal migration” (Figures 3a, 3b) and “State Border Guard Service, job descriptions” (Figures 4a, 4b).

2-3: Trends in combating smuggling at the border

As shown in Figures 2a and 2b, the graph of the dynamics of court decisions on smuggling has a weak upward trend with a probability of $R^2 = 0.5099$. The detection of

²⁴ Unified State Register of Court Decisions. [Id.](#)

smuggling at the borders increased after the adoption of the Law of Ukraine “On Border Control” in 2010, and in 2011 the detection of smuggling-related offences reached its highest level. Detection of illegal migrants also reached its highest level in 2011 (Figure 3a). Protocols were also signed with the Chief Commandant of the Border Guard of the Republic of Poland and the Government of the Republic of Moldova on joint border patrols during this period. In 2009, cooperation was established with the border guard services of neighbouring countries and Frontex, which facilitated the exchange of information on illegal activities at the borders. In 2011, Presidential Decree No. 494 on the Integrated Border Management Strategy was also signed, which included implementing a risk analysis system and international cooperation. The combination of these measures helped to reduce the level of smuggling and illegal migration crimes by 2015. However, in 2016, the level of detected crimes involving the movement of smuggled goods began to increase. This trend is attributed to the introduction of the latest border management technologies, border aviation development and mobile teams’ work since 2015. Nevertheless, no downward trend in smuggling-related crimes has been detected in recent years, which suggests the need to strengthen legislative initiatives to prevent these crimes.

Figure 2. Dynamics (a) and trend line (b) of court decisions on the request “State Border Guard Service, smuggling”

Source: Created by the author based on the Unified State Register of Court Decisions²⁵

2-4: TRENDS IN COMBATING ILLEGAL MIGRATION

As for irregular migration, as can be seen from Figures 3a and 3b, the trend is not linear. It is characterised by a weak level of forecasting with the probability of an increase in irregular migration $R^2 = 0.3993$. However, from 2018 to 2021, there was a downward trend in irregular migration, possibly due to the introduction of the visa-free regime in 2017. At the same time, cases of illegal cross-border movement have begun to increase again in recent years. These cases mainly involve men who cannot travel abroad during martial law and try to illegally enter neighbouring countries.

Figure 3. Dynamics (a) and trend line (b) of court decisions on the request “State Border Guard Service, illegal migration”

Source: Created by the author based on the Unified State Register of Court Decisions²⁶

2-5: TRENDS IN VIOLATIONS OF JOB INSTRUCTIONS BY TRAFFIC POLICE EMPLOYEES

The dynamics of court decisions concerning the SBGS job descriptions are shown in Figures 4a and 4b. As can be seen from the graphs, the dynamics of court decisions concerning violations of job descriptions are described by an exponential relationship with a probability of further growth $R^2 = 0.949$. Despite the approval of the Instruction on the Procedure for the Actions of the SBGS Officials in 2016, violations of job descriptions, which consist of actions or omissions of SBGS employees that lead to the commission of cross-border crimes or increase the risk of cross-border crimes, continue to grow. The increase in violations of job descriptions during martial law may also be related to the increased risks and requirements for border guard service members directly related to armed protection of the state border.

Figure 4. Dynamics (a) and trend line (b) of court decisions on the request “State Border Guard Service, job descriptions”

Source: Created by the author based on the Unified State Register of Court Decisions²⁷

²⁶ Unified State Register of Court Decisions. [Id.](#)

²⁷ Unified State Register of Court Decisions. [Id.](#)

Thus, the analysis of the effectiveness of legal acts in preventing offences at the state border of Ukraine based on the assessment of the dynamics of court cases revealed a tendency to increase the number of court cases with the request “State Border Guard Service” and “job descriptions”. The growth of cases involving the SBGS is explained by the insufficient effectiveness of preventive measures introduced based on existing regulations, especially in cases of violations of job descriptions, which may indicate an insufficient level of anti-corruption in the SBGS and may be due to new challenges during the period of martial law. At the same time, preventing smuggling and illegal migration also does not demonstrate significant effectiveness, requiring more effective legislative initiatives to combat these crimes.

2-6:REASONS FOR INSUFFICIENT EFFECTIVENESS IN COMBATING CRIME AT THE BORDER AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM, INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE.

Our study found an increase in the number of court decisions concerning the State Border Guard Service. In 2011, we found the highest level of court decisions related to smuggling and illegal migrants, followed by a subsequent decline, which coincided with a period of active international cooperation. The study of international cooperation in combating cross-border crime is important in research²⁸. Russo and Stambøl²⁹ studied the EU’s preventive policy on cross-border crime and found that EU programmes aim to prevent crime within the EU’s jurisdiction through the impact on third countries, namely training, funding, and reforming law enforcement agencies in third countries. In this way, the EU carries out preventive measures at a distance, reducing organised crime risks in EU member states.

The growth of court decisions related to the SBGS indicates active efforts to monitor compliance with the rules at the borders. However, it demonstrates the insufficient effectiveness of preventive measures, especially in preventing violations of job descriptions. The problem of corruption in the border and customs services is significant. Kim and Tajima³⁰ demonstrated the role of corruption in facilitating smuggling, which reduces the overall volume of smuggling, but only in statistical data, not in real life. At the same time, the problem of corruption among border and customs officials is not unique to economically underdeveloped countries; it is found even in the United States. Even though the issue of corruption on the southern border of the United

²⁸ Ilchyshyn, N., Brusakova, O., Krykun, V., & Myroshnychenko, Y. (2023). International Legal Cooperation in the Field Of Criminal Justice: New Challenges and Ways to Overcome Them. *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 11(4), e767-e767. <https://doi.org/10.55908/sdgs.v11i4.767>

²⁹ Russo, A., & Stambøl, E. M. (2022). The external dimension of the EU's fight against transnational crime: Transferring political rationalities of crime control. *Review of International Studies*, 48(2), 326-345. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0260210521000358>

³⁰ Kim, D., & Tajima, Y. (2022). Smuggling and border enforcement. *International Organisation*, 76(4), 830-867. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002081832200011X>

States has not been sufficiently studied, Jancsics³¹ still identified patterns of officials involved in corruption. Namely, it was determined that customs officers with less experience were associated with corrupt schemes in the drug trade. At the same time, their senior colleagues were more likely to receive undue benefits from facilitating illegal migration. Meanwhile, fighting corruption at the borders increases a country's GDP and promotes economic development^{32, 33}.

CONCLUSION

3.

Our study found many legal acts and initiatives to prevent offences, including patrolling, border management, cooperation with international and national agencies, service development, and regulation of the powers of SBGS officials. However, the identified legal documents proved insufficiently effective in preventing smuggling and illegal migration, although we found positive trends in 2011–2015 related to active international cooperation during this period. The low effectiveness of preventive measures against offences in the border area was also confirmed by the growing trends in court decisions related to the State Border Guard Service and violations of job descriptions. While the increase in court cases related to the SBGS may indicate more significant activity in combating violations at the state border, the increase in cases of violations of job descriptions indicates the need to update job descriptions to reflect new requirements related to martial law and reduce corruption risks.

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³¹ Jancsics, D. (2021). Law enforcement corruption along the US borders. *Security Journal*, 34, 26-46. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41284-019-00203-8>

³² Ortiz, T. R. (2021). Bribery and Corruption at the Border: Mexico: An Outstanding Challenge to Be Overcome by the Mexican Government. *Global Trade and Customs Journal*, 16(9). <https://doi.org/10.54648/gtcj2021048>

³³ Kitsios, E., Jalles, J. T., & Verdier, G. (2022). Tax evasion from cross-border fraud: does digitalisation make a difference? *Applied Economics Letters*, 30(10), 1400-1406. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2022.2056566>

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